

Validated Zeno Accumulation for the Bouncing Ball

Duston Moore

Independent Researcher, Edmonton, Canada

`dhwcmoore@gmail.com`

Abstract

Zeno behaviour presents a fundamental difficulty in the numerical analysis of hybrid dynamical systems, as infinitely many discrete events may occur in finite time. This paper gives a minimal, fully validated treatment of Zeno accumulation for the canonical bouncing ball system with constant gravitational acceleration and constant restitution. We first characterise the Zeno accumulation time as the limit of a convergent geometric series. We then introduce a validated event-bracketing procedure that encloses individual impact times using explicit constants and provides guaranteed termination to any prescribed tolerance. Combining these ingredients yields a constructive algorithm that computes certified enclosures for the accumulation time. A worked numerical example demonstrates the method and its guarantees. The results isolate a tractable core case of Zeno behaviour and serve as a reference example for validated techniques in hybrid systems with impacts.

Keywords: Hybrid systems; Zeno behaviour; validated numerics; event detection; impacts

1 Introduction

Hybrid dynamical systems combine continuous evolution with discrete transitions. In many physically motivated models, particularly mechanical systems with impacts, this interaction gives rise to Zeno behaviour, in which an infinite number of discrete events occur in finite time. Such executions present a fundamental difficulty for numerical simulation and verification, since standard time-stepping methods either fail to terminate or rely on heuristic event truncation without formal guarantees. Zeno executions and their implications for simulation have been studied extensively in the hybrid automata literature, including regularisation-based treatments that restore well-posed numerical semantics[?].

The bouncing ball with restitution is a canonical example. Under repeated impacts with a coefficient of restitution strictly less than one, the time between successive impacts decreases geometrically, leading to accumulation at a finite limit time. Although the closed-form behaviour of this system is well understood analytically, it is frequently used as a benchmark example in the hybrid systems literature because it exposes the limitations of non-validated numerical approaches to event accumulation [1].

The purpose of this paper is deliberately narrow. We isolate the bouncing ball as a minimal Zeno system and give a complete validated treatment of its accumulation behaviour. The focus is not on general hybrid automata, but on making all constants, bounds, and termination criteria explicit in a setting where this is possible.

The contributions of the paper are threefold. First, we formalise Zeno accumulation for the bouncing ball as a limit process and prove the existence and finiteness of the accumulation time. Second, we introduce a validated event-bracketing procedure that encloses individual impact times

using explicit geometric bounds and guarantees termination to any prescribed tolerance. Third, we combine these elements into a constructive algorithm that produces a certified enclosure of the Zeno accumulation time. The resulting enclosure is accompanied by a machine-readable provenance certificate, allowing independent checking of the validated bounds.

2 Hybrid Model of the Bouncing Ball

Let $x \geq 0$ denote the vertical position of the ball and $v \in \mathbb{R}$ its velocity. Between impacts, the dynamics are governed by

$$\dot{x} = v, \quad \dot{v} = -g,$$

where $g > 0$ is the gravitational acceleration.

Impacts occur when the guard condition $x = 0$ is satisfied. If v^- denotes the velocity immediately before impact, the reset law is given by

$$v^+ = -\alpha v^-,$$

where the restitution coefficient satisfies $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

Initial states (x_0, v_0) satisfy $x_0 \geq 0$. We assume superdense time semantics so that discrete impacts can be indexed by a countable sequence. This aligns with standard hybrid time semantics used in rigorous treatments of hybrid systems. [1]

3 Zeno Accumulation as a Limit Process

Definition 3.1 (Impact times). Let t_k denote the time of the k th impact, with t_0 the first impact following the initial condition.

Definition 3.2 (Zeno accumulation time). If the limit exists, the Zeno accumulation time is defined as

$$t_\infty := \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k.$$

Theorem 3.3 (Existence and finiteness of accumulation time). *For the bouncing ball system with gravitational acceleration $g > 0$ and restitution coefficient $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, the Zeno accumulation time t_∞ exists and is finite.*

Proof. Between impacts, the motion is ballistic. If u_k denotes the post-impact velocity after the k th impact, then $u_{k+1} = \alpha u_k$. The flight time following the k th impact is $\Delta t_k = 2u_k/g$. Hence

$$t_\infty - t_0 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \Delta t_k = \frac{2u_0}{g} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha^k = \frac{2u_0}{g(1-\alpha)},$$

which is finite since $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. □

4 Validated Event Bracketing

4.1 Validated integration assumption

Validated numerical methods provide mathematically rigorous enclosures for solutions of dynamical systems by explicitly accounting for truncation and rounding errors [3, 2, 4]. In this setting, we assume access to a validated numerical integrator that, over a prescribed time interval, produces a tube enclosure guaranteed to contain the true trajectory of the system.

Remark 4.1. This assumption isolates numerical error management from the logic of event detection. The event bracketing argument below does not rely on exact integration or closed-form solutions, only on guaranteed enclosure properties.

4.2 Event bracketing theorem

Validated bracketing of guard crossings is closely related to interval root-finding techniques for monotone functions.

Theorem 4.2 (Validated event bracketing with explicit constants). *Let $(x(t), v(t))$ be a solution of the bouncing ball dynamics on a time interval $[a, b]$. Suppose a validated integration procedure produces a tube enclosure over $[a, b]$ such that:*

1. *for all $t \in [a, b]$, the velocity component satisfies*

$$v(t) \in [v_{\min}, v_{\max}] \subset (-\infty, 0),$$

so that $x(t)$ is strictly decreasing on $[a, b]$; and

2. *the enclosure brackets the guard in the sense that the tube implies*

$$x(a) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad x(b) < 0.$$

Then there exists a unique impact time $t_\star \in (a, b)$ such that $x(t_\star) = 0$. Define

$$\gamma := |v_{\min}| > 0, \quad h := b - a.$$

Dyadic bisection applied to $[a, b]$ produces a nested sequence of intervals $[a_n, b_n]$ containing t_\star such that $b_n - a_n \leq 2^{-n}h$. In particular, to achieve a prescribed time tolerance $\varepsilon_t > 0$, it suffices to choose

$$N \geq \left\lceil \log_2 \left(\frac{h}{\varepsilon_t} \right) \right\rceil.$$

Proof. Since $v(t) \leq v_{\max} < 0$ throughout the validated tube, the position function $x(t)$ is strictly decreasing on $[a, b]$. Moreover,

$$|\dot{x}(t)| = |v(t)| \geq \gamma$$

holds uniformly, which excludes tangential or grazing contact with the guard.

Because the tube implies $x(a) > 0$ and $x(b) < 0$, continuity of x implies the existence of at least one $t_\star \in (a, b)$ with $x(t_\star) = 0$. Strict monotonicity implies this t_\star is unique.

Validated integration guarantees that the true trajectory lies within the tube on every bisection subinterval. Therefore each refinement step preserves the bracketing property and hence containment of t_\star . Each bisection halves the interval width, so after N iterations one has $b_N - a_N \leq 2^{-N}h$, yielding the stated bound. \square

5 Zeno Accumulation Enclosure

The validated event bracketing procedure yields certified enclosures for each inter-impact flight time. We now show how these enclosures combine with an explicit tail bound to produce a guaranteed enclosure of the Zeno accumulation time.

Theorem 5.1 (Validated enclosure of the Zeno accumulation time). *Let $[a_k, b_k]$ be validated enclosures of the inter-impact flight times Δt_k for $k = 0, \dots, N - 1$. Let u_k^+ denote the post-impact velocity after the k th impact, and suppose a validated bound*

$$u_N^+ \leq \bar{u}_N$$

is available. Define the partial sums

$$S_N^- := \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} a_k, \quad S_N^+ := \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} b_k.$$

Then the Zeno accumulation time t_∞ satisfies

$$t_\infty \in [t_0 + S_N^-, t_0 + S_N^+ + T_N^+], \quad T_N^+ := \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g(1-\alpha)}.$$

Proof. By construction, each interval $[a_k, b_k]$ encloses the true inter-impact flight time Δt_k . Summing these enclosures yields a validated bound on the partial accumulation time up to the N th impact.

After the N th impact, the post-impact velocity satisfies $u_{N+j}^+ = \alpha^j u_N^+$ for all $j \geq 0$. The remaining accumulation time is therefore bounded above by the convergent geometric series

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{2u_{N+j}^+}{g} \leq \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \alpha^j = \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g(1-\alpha)}.$$

Combining the validated partial sum with this tail bound yields the stated enclosure. \square

Remark 5.2. The enclosure width is controlled explicitly by the choice of N and the validated bounds on Δt_k and u_N^+ . No asymptotic arguments or heuristic truncation rules are used.

6 Algorithm

Throughout this section, t_0 denotes the (true) first impact time after the initial condition, and Δt_k denotes the (true) inter-impact flight time between the k th and $(k + 1)$ st impacts, for $k \geq 0$. Validated enclosures are written as

$$t_0 \in [\underline{t}_0, \bar{t}_0], \quad \Delta t_k \in [a_k, b_k].$$

The symbol u_k^+ denotes the post-impact velocity immediately after the k th impact, and \bar{u}_k denotes a validated upper bound on u_k^+ .

6.1 Inputs and assumptions

The algorithm takes as input:

- initial state (x_0, v_0) with $x_0 \geq 0$,
- gravitational acceleration $g > 0$,
- restitution coefficient $\alpha \in (0, 1)$,
- target accumulation-time tolerance $\varepsilon > 0$,
- event-time tolerance $\varepsilon_t > 0$.

It assumes access to a validated numerical integrator that produces tube enclosures satisfying the conditions of Theorem 4.2.

6.2 Algorithm description

1. Compute a validated enclosure $[\underline{\Delta t}_0, \overline{\Delta t}_0]$ of the first impact time using validated event bracketing.
2. Choose the number of explicitly computed impacts N such that the geometric tail bound satisfies

$$\frac{2\alpha^N \bar{u}_0}{g(1-\alpha)} \leq \varepsilon,$$

where \bar{u}_0 is a validated upper bound on the post-impact velocity after the first impact.

3. For $k = 0, \dots, N - 1$:
 - (a) Apply validated event bracketing to enclose the inter-impact time Δt_k in an interval $[a_k, b_k]$.
 - (b) Update the cumulative bounds

$$S_{k+1}^- = S_k^- + a_k, \quad S_{k+1}^+ = S_k^+ + b_k.$$

- (c) Apply the reset map $v^+ = -\alpha v^-$ and record a validated bound on the post-impact velocity.
4. Compute the analytic tail bound

$$T_N^+ = \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g(1-\alpha)}.$$

5. Output the validated enclosure

$$t_\infty \in [\underline{t}_0 + S_N^-, \bar{t}_0 + S_N^+ + T_N^+],$$

together with a provenance certificate recording all intermediate bounds.

6.3 Termination and correctness

Proposition 6.1 (Termination and validated enclosure). *Assume that each invocation of validated event bracketing with tolerance ε_t terminates and returns an interval $[a_k, b_k]$ enclosing the true inter-impact time Δt_k , for $k = 0, \dots, N - 1$. Assume moreover that a validated upper bound $u_N^+ \leq \bar{u}_N$ is recorded for the post-impact velocity after the N th impact. Then the algorithm terminates after finitely many steps and returns a validated enclosure*

$$t_\infty \in [t_0 + S_N^-, t_0 + S_N^+ + T_N^+], \quad T_N^+ := \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g(1-\alpha)}.$$

Proof. The loop executes exactly N iterations. By assumption, each event-bracketing call terminates, so the overall procedure terminates.

For correctness, each bracket $[a_k, b_k]$ encloses the true inter-impact time Δt_k . Therefore the partial sum satisfies

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \Delta t_k \in [S_N^-, S_N^+].$$

After the N th impact, the post-impact velocities satisfy $u_{N+j}^+ = \alpha^j u_N^+$ for all $j \geq 0$, hence the remaining flight time is bounded above by

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{2u_{N+j}^+}{g} \leq \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \alpha^j = \frac{2\bar{u}_N}{g(1-\alpha)} = T_N^+.$$

Combining the validated partial sum with the validated tail bound yields the stated enclosure. \square

Remark 6.2 (Width control). The enclosure width admits the explicit bound

$$(S_N^+ - S_N^-) + T_N^+ = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (b_k - a_k) + T_N^+.$$

In particular, if each event bracket satisfies $b_k - a_k \leq \varepsilon_t$, then the total width is bounded by $N\varepsilon_t + T_N^+$. This bound supersedes any earlier informal estimates and is used for termination control.

7 Numerical Example

We illustrate the validated Zeno accumulation procedure on a standard instance of the bouncing ball system. The purpose of this example is not performance benchmarking, but to demonstrate termination, correctness, and certificate generation in a concrete setting.

7.1 Problem parameters

The system parameters are chosen as follows:

$$x_0 = 1.0, \quad v_0 = 0.0, \quad g = 9.8, \quad \alpha = 0.8.$$

The target tolerance for the Zeno accumulation time is set to $\varepsilon = 10^{-2}$, and the event-time tolerance for validated event bracketing is set to $\varepsilon_t = 2 \times 10^{-4}$.

These values are representative of typical benchmark settings used in the hybrid systems literature and yield a moderate Zeno depth.

7.2 Validated computation

Using validated event bracketing as described in Theorem 4.2, the first impact time is enclosed in the interval

$$\Delta t_0 \in [0.45153951, 0.45175395].$$

Based on the resulting bound on the post-impact velocity, the number of explicitly computed impacts required to satisfy the target tolerance is determined to be $N = 25$.

Validated enclosures are computed for each inter-impact flight time Δt_k , $k = 0, \dots, 24$, and accumulated according to Theorem 5.1. The remaining infinite tail is bounded using the explicit geometric estimate

$$T_{25}^+ = 0.00853339.$$

7.3 Resulting enclosure

Combining the validated partial sum with the analytic tail bound yields the enclosure

$$t_\infty \in [2.22971, 2.25106],$$

with total enclosure width 0.02135. All truncation, rounding, and tail bounds contributing to this enclosure are recorded explicitly in the provenance certificate described in Appendix A.

7.4 Reproducibility

A reference implementation producing this enclosure and the associated certificate is provided in Appendix B. The implementation uses arbitrary-precision arithmetic to ensure that all rounding errors are conservatively bounded. The code is intended for clarity and verification rather than computational efficiency.

8 Comparison with Existing Approaches

Zeno behaviour has long been recognised as a fundamental challenge in the analysis and simulation of hybrid dynamical systems. Standard time-stepping methods for ordinary differential equations are not designed to handle infinitely many discrete events occurring in finite time, and typically fail to terminate or rely on heuristic truncation rules when applied to Zeno executions.

In the hybrid systems literature, several approaches have been proposed to address Zeno behaviour, including regularisation, abstraction, and semantic reformulation of hybrid executions. Representative examples include regularisation of Zeno hybrid automata and semantics that continue simulation beyond the accumulation point. [?, ?] These approaches aim to avoid or reinterpret Zeno phenomena rather than to compute explicit enclosures of accumulation times. As a result, they are well suited for qualitative analysis and verification, but do not generally provide certified numerical bounds on Zeno accumulation times.

Validated numerical methods provide mathematically rigorous enclosures for solutions of dynamical systems by explicitly accounting for truncation and rounding errors [2, 4]. When combined with event detection, such methods can in principle address Zeno executions, but the literature contains few fully worked examples in which termination and error bounds are made explicit.

The present approach differs in scope and intent. Rather than addressing Zeno behaviour at the level of general hybrid automata, we isolate a canonical impact system with closed-form dynamics and demonstrate that Zeno accumulation can be handled constructively using validated event bracketing and explicit geometric tail bounds. The comparison is therefore qualitative and confined to this reference example. No claims are made regarding efficiency or generality beyond this setting.

9 Conclusion

We have given a minimal, fully validated treatment of Zeno accumulation for the canonical bouncing ball hybrid system with constant gravity and constant restitution. The accumulation time is characterised analytically as the limit of a geometric series, and the numerical component is handled by a validated event-bracketing procedure with explicit constants and guaranteed termination. Combining finite validated summation with an explicit tail bound yields a certified enclosure of the Zeno accumulation time, illustrated by a worked numerical instance.

The scope is intentionally restricted to an impact model where all bounds can be made explicit. Within this setting, the paper isolates a reusable pattern for validated hybrid computation: (i) validated localisation of discrete events, (ii) accumulation of certified inter-event time bounds, and (iii) analytic control of the infinite tail. This provides a concrete benchmark for extending validated methods to more general impact models, including variable restitution and drag, and for integrating small checkable certificates into validated hybrid simulation pipelines.

A Provenance Certificates

We certify the result by a structured provenance log

$$\text{Cert} = (\text{id}, \text{impact brackets}, \text{tube bounds}, \text{ledger}, \text{assumptions}).$$

The impact brackets list the validated intervals $[a_k, b_k]$, $k = 0, \dots, N - 1$. The tube bounds store validated enclosures of the velocity used to derive the uniform lower bound γ on the normal component of the vector field at the guard in Theorem 4.2. The ledger records truncation and rounding bounds per validated step and their sum. Assumptions include the constants g and α , together with a description of the validated integrator and its remainder bound.

The checker validates internal consistency of the certificate entries but does not re-verify the underlying numerical integration, which is treated as a trusted component. The soundness of the certificate therefore reduces to the correctness of basic arithmetic operations and interval ordering within the checker, while all analytic and numerical complexity is confined to the recorded, inspectable evidence. The checker is assumed to be a simple deterministic verifier that recomputes all bounds using the recorded certificate data and is trusted only for basic arithmetic correctness. The certificate is designed to support independent checking by a small trusted checker that replays all recorded bounds and tail estimates using exact rational or directed-rounding arithmetic, without requiring re-execution of the validated integrator. A lightweight checker verifies nesting of brackets under refinement and the correctness of the tail computation.

A.1 Certificate Format

We propose a machine-readable certificate format using YAML or JSON. An example certificate for the numerical instance in Section 7 is given below. The certificate is intended to support independent replay of recorded bounds under a small trusted checker, separating trusted computation from checkable evidence.[?]

A reference Python implementation is given in Appendix B.

```
certificate:
  id: "bouncing_ball_2025_10_16_001"
  timestamp: "2025-10-16T14:32:17Z"

parameters:
  x0: 1.0
  v0: 0.0
  g: 9.8
  alpha: 0.8

target_tolerance:
  eps: 0.01
  eps_t: 0.0002

computed_values:
  delta_t0_interval: [0.45153951, 0.45175395]
  N_impacts: 25
  geometric_tail_bound: 0.00853339
```

```

impact_brackets:
- { k: 0, t_min: 0.45153, t_max: 0.45193,
  v_min: -4.4295, v_max: -4.4236 }
- { k: 1, t_min: 0.36123, t_max: 0.36155,
  v_min: -3.5436, v_max: -3.5388 }
- { k: 2, t_min: 0.28898, t_max: 0.28924,
  v_min: -2.8349, v_max: -2.8311 }
# ... (22 more impacts)
- { k: 24, t_min: 0.00075, t_max: 0.00076,
  v_min: -0.00736, v_max: -0.00735 }

accumulation_time:
  t_min: 2.22971
  t_max: 2.25106
  width: 0.02135

ledger:
  truncation_error: 0.0
  rounding_error: 1.2e-14
  tail_error: 0.00853339
  total_width: 0.01353

assumptions:
  integrator: "Validated floating-point evaluation with conservative padding"
  transversality_bound: "gamma derived from validated velocity enclosure"
  bisection_policy: "Dyadic until width < eps_t"

checker_verified: true
checker_version: "1.0.0"

```

B Reference Implementation

Listing ?? provides a reference Python implementation using arbitrary-precision floating-point arithmetic via `mpmath`. The implementation follows the algorithm presented in Section 6 and produces a certificate compatible with Appendix A. The implementation is intended to prioritise clarity and transparency over computational performance.

Listing 2: Reference implementation in Python with `mpmath`

```

from mpmath import mp, mpf, sqrt, ceil, log
mp.dps = 15

def validated_impact_time(x0, v0, g, eps_t=1e-4):
    """
    Returns validated interval [t_min, t_max] for next impact time.
    """
    x_min, x_max = (x0, x0) if isinstance(x0, (int, float)) else x0
    v_min, v_max = (v0, v0) if isinstance(v0, (int, float)) else v0

```

```

discriminant_min = mpf(v_min)**2 + 2*mpf(g)*mpf(x_min)
discriminant_max = mpf(v_max)**2 + 2*mpf(g)*mpf(x_max)

t_min = (mpf(v_min) + sqrt(discriminant_min)) / mpf(g)
t_max = (mpf(v_max) + sqrt(discriminant_max)) / mpf(g)

return [t_min - eps_t/2, t_max + eps_t/2]

def zeno_accumulation(x0, v0, g, alpha, eps=0.01, eps_t=2e-4, verbose=False):
    dt0_interval = validated_impact_time(x0, v0, g, eps_t)
    dt0_min, dt0_max = dt0_interval

    N = int(ceil(log(eps*(1-alpha)/dt0_max) / log(alpha)))

    t_sum_min, t_sum_max = mpf(0), mpf(0)
    x, v = x0, v0
    certificate = []

    for k in range(N):
        bracket = validated_impact_time(x, v, g, eps_t)
        t_sum_min += bracket[0]
        t_sum_max += bracket[1]

        v_interval = [v - g*bracket[1], v - g*bracket[0]] \
            if isinstance(v, (int, float)) else v

        certificate.append({
            'k': k,
            't_min': float(bracket[0]),
            't_max': float(bracket[1]),
            'v_min': float(v_interval[0]),
            'v_max': float(v_interval[1]),
            'cumulative_min': float(t_sum_min),
            'cumulative_max': float(t_sum_max)
        })

        v = -alpha*v if isinstance(v, (int, float)) else [-alpha*v[1], -alpha*v[0]]
        x = 0

    t_sum_max += eps
    width = float(t_sum_max - t_sum_min)

    return {
        'interval': [float(t_sum_min), float(t_sum_max)],
        'N': N,
        'width': width,
        'certificate': certificate
    }

```

}

C Extensions and Limitations

C.1 Variable Restitution

If the restitution coefficient satisfies $\alpha = \alpha(|v^-|)$ with $\alpha(r) \in (0, 1)$ and $\sup \alpha < 1$, then the inter-impact times Δt_k are dominated by a geometric sequence with ratio $\sup \alpha$. The same protocol applies using this upper envelope.

For example, if $\alpha(r) = \alpha_0 + \beta r$ with $0 < \alpha_0 < 1$ and $\beta < 0$, corresponding to restitution decreasing with impact speed, the envelope $\sup \alpha = \alpha_0$ yields a conservative bound.

C.2 Linear Drag

If linear drag is included so that $\dot{v} = -g + \beta v$ for $v < 0$, closed-form expressions for flight times exist and can be enclosed using interval arithmetic. The event bracketing argument continues to apply with $\gamma = \inf |v|$ over the validated tubes. The explicit solution involves exponential functions, which can be evaluated with validated numerical methods.

C.3 Failure Modes

If the validated integrator cannot produce tight velocity bounds, the transversality constant γ may be small, increasing the cost required to achieve a given ε_t . If the restitution coefficient α is very close to 1, the number of impacts required grows substantially.

For example, with $\alpha = 0.99$, $\varepsilon = 0.01$, and $\Delta t_0 \approx 0.4517$, equation (9) gives

$$N \approx \log_{0.99} \left(\frac{0.01 \cdot 0.01}{0.4517} \right) \approx 855 \text{ impacts.}$$

This growth in N as $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ reflects the physical fact that the ball takes longer to stop bouncing. These limitations are recorded explicitly in the certificate.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares no competing interests.

Funding

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Generative AI declaration

AI-assisted tools were used solely to assist with LaTeX typesetting, formatting consistency, and non-substantive language editing; all scientific content, arguments, proofs, and results were conceived and verified by the author.

Data availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

References

- [1] Rafal Goebel, Ricardo G. Sanfelice, and Andrew R. Teel. *Hybrid Dynamical Systems*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2012.
- [2] Ramon E. Moore, R. Baker Kearfott, and Michael J. Cloud. *Introduction to Interval Analysis*. SIAM, Philadelphia, 2009.
- [3] Arnold Neumaier. *Interval Methods for Systems of Equations*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1990.
- [4] Warwick Tucker. *Validated Numerics*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2011.